

Analysing Gazan Victimhood on Social Media: A Discursive Study through Van Dijk’s Socio-Cognitive Framework

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Abstract

This article explores the discursive construction of victimhood on social media, specifically examining how the experiences of people living in Gaza are represented on Facebook. Drawing on van Dijk’s socio-cognitive framework, this study employed a thematic approach to analyse a dataset of 95 Facebook postings made by Gazans in response to the war following October 7, 2023. Data analysis revealed five themes that were central to Gazan victimhood. These themes include the negative other, deprivation of fundamental rights, sense of loss, positive self-description, and satisfaction with fate. While these themes emphasise the paucity of essentials, the profound loss of loved ones, and the view of others as hostile or indifferent, they also illuminate the resilience of the Gazan populace and their satisfaction with their destiny. Eight discursive strategies emerge in the identified themes: polarisation, concretisation, compassion move, self-identity descriptions, negative lexicalisation, victimisation, hyperbole, and warning. These strategies are intricately linked to the semantic and contextual models posited by van Dijk’s socio-cognitive framework. Constructing Gazans’ victimhood enhances their positive self-image, while fostering a negative image of the other. This study is hoped to enhance our understanding of how social media postings can be leveraged to construct and communicate the concept of victimhood.

Keywords

Victimhood, Gazan people, social media, critical studies, critical realism

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Introduction

The Palestinian-Israeli conflict is one of the most significant and old national liberation struggles in the Middle East. The Gaza War, which erupted in October 2023, is the most recent of numerous conflicts that have ensued since the establishment of the Israeli state in 1948. This incident all began on October 7, 2023, when Hamas fighters crossed the border between Israel and Gaza. Hamas fighters eliminated the security forces patrolling the area, resulting in the deaths of 1400 Israelis. Additionally, 294 hostages were taken. Israel shut Gaza's borders and disconnected its electricity on October 8, 2023. Their demand was for the hostages to be released. The Israeli military then launched numerous airstrikes against Hamas strongholds, deeply embedded in the densely populated civilian neighbourhoods. On November 1, 2023, Israel launched a ground incursion into Gaza. The assault resulted in the deaths and injuries of thousands of Gazan civilians. Since then, the people of Gaza have endured suffering. The absence of food, clean water, shelter, and fundamental necessities of life has persisted.

Social media has become a powerful tool for sharing personal stories and experiences, especially during times of conflict. For the people of Gaza, platforms like Facebook offer a way to communicate their struggles, emotions, and resilience to the world. Yet, how these stories of hardship and victimhood are told, understood, and spread is shaped by the language and strategies people use to describe their experiences. This study looks closely at how Gazans, in response to the war that began after October 7, 2023, use Facebook to present themselves as victims.

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While much research has focused on how the media portrays conflict, less attention has been given to how everyday people, like those living in Gaza, construct their small stories on social media. This is where our research aims to make a difference. It examines not only what Gazans are saying but how they are saying it – the strategies they use to convey their suffering, loss, and resilience. By applying van Dijk's socio-cognitive framework (2014, 2018), which explores how language reflects our mental processes and social environments, we explore Gazans' discursive strategies to communicate their victimhood. These strategies do not just represent their suffering but also shape how their stories are received and understood by a global audience.

The significance of our study lies in its potential to shed light on how victimhood is constructed in digital spaces, where voices from conflict zones can bypass traditional media filters. By analysing 95 Facebook posts, we aim to understand the patterns in the language used by Gazans – including themes of loss, deprivation of rights, and self-identity – and how these themes foster empathy, solidarity, or even opposition among audiences. The findings of this study will contribute to broader discussions on how social media shapes perceptions of victimhood, particularly in regions of conflict, and how these perceptions can influence public opinion and international discourse.

Through this research, we seek to answer the following question:

How is victimhood constructed in the Facebook postings made by Gazans in response to the war following October 7, 2023?

In answering this question, we hope to not only highlight the importance of language in shaping perceptions of conflict but also show how social media can be a space where marginalised voices are heard, and where new forms of storytelling and identity-building emerge.

1. Literature Review

This section begins with the conceptualisation of victimhood, which is the focus of this study. It then proceeds with a concise overview of van Dijk’s socio-cognitive approach, which serves as the theoretical foundation for this research. Finally, it synthesises relevant literature pertaining to social media and the voices of victims.

1.1. Victimhood

Victimhood is often considered to be a component of human suffering. According to Campbell and Manning (2018), social status is gained by being a victim, whereas privilege is viewed as a negative trait. Victims must identify with and claim victimhood to become victims (Mohammed Na’aim et al., 2019; Thunberg, 2020; Krystalli, 2021; Foringer, 2023), while also ensuring that others acknowledge and validate their victim status (Strobl, 2010; Chouliaraki, 2021). Holstein and Miller (1990) investigated the continuing social dynamics and conditions underlying the practices through which we assign victim status to ourselves and to others. To gain an understanding of privilege, it is most effective to apply the principles of universal human rights to select groups that publicly reject their privileged status (Gordon, 2004; Armaly and Enders, 2022; Gray and Kubin, 2024). Miranda et al. (2009) contend that privilege plays a role in the systemic barriers encountered by those who do not possess a certain privilege, thereby sustaining or strengthening inequality.

Victimhood is the foundational framework for constructing human rights systems (Illouz, 2003; Dolhan et al., 2021; Gray and Kubin, 2024). It is not solely a societal virtue but also a means of empowerment. Berbrier (2000) states that interest groups can exaggerate the perception of suffering when romanticising victims. Owing to the allure of victim fashion, interest groups may engage in the perverse practice of victim monetisation. Similarly, Jensen and Ronsbo (2014) suggest that victimhood is influenced by changing power dynamics, which calls into question the identities of individuals involved. Cole (2007) observed that a significant aspect of the current discourse is the shift in the claims of victimhood. Consequently, those who express their encounters with injustice are progressively being categorised as perpetrators of oppression.

Globally, civilians are deliberately targeted and victimised as strategic components of warfare. Over the past three decades of internal armed conflict, armed groups have intentionally targeted and killed approximately one million civilians (Pettersson and Öberg, 2020; Al-Ramahi and Rashid, 2024). Bombings, massacres, and killings are ways in which civilians are targeted and victimised (Stanton, 2013; Polo and Gleditsch, 2016). Several scholars have investigated the factors behind the victimisation of civilians.

Valentino (2014) argues that targeting civilians during combat is neither unreasonable nor arbitrary. Valentino (2014) distinguished between two narratives: a war narrative, which highlights the ways in which war encourages the deliberate targeting of people, and a political narrative, which examines the reasons why political leaders endorse violence against civilians. Similarly, Wood (2018) classified acts of premeditated violence against civilians into distinct categories according to the goals of combatants and the mindset of the militant group's leadership. Elizur and Yishay-Krien (2009) investigated the psychological mechanisms implicated in victims' experiences such as dehumanisation. They also examined the psychological mechanisms employed by perpetrators, such as moral detachment and the acceptance of inflicting fatalities. We argue that these mechanisms played a role in the occurrence of violent acts carried out by Israeli soldiers in Gaza. The purpose of the present investigation is to examine the discursive construction of victimhood through small stories, remarks, and prayers dedicated to the Gazans.

This study adds to the existing body of knowledge on victimhood by deciphering the victim's language and identifying the discursive strategies that help build Gazans' victimhood.

1.2. Van Dijk's Socio-cognitive Framework

The primary objective of critical discourse analysis, as outlined by van Dijk (2001), is to examine how power, domination, and inequality are manifested, perpetuated, and challenged using language and text. Critical discourse analysis was formulated to gain a deeper understanding of the discursive mechanisms that create, maintain, and perpetuate symmetrical power dynamics (van Dijk, 1997). Van Dijk (2018) introduced a socio-cognitive paradigm that emphasises the cognitive aspects of discourse creation and understanding. According to van Dijk (2015), there is no direct relationship between discourse and social structures. The mental representation of language users, both as people and members of society, is the cognitive interface through which discourse functions.

Van Dijk's socio-cognitive framework (1995, 2001, 2014, 2018) is useful in identifying the discursive strategies deployed in Gazans' small stories, remarks, and prayers that appeared in social media postings. The utilisation of van Dijk's (2014, 2018) semantic or situation models aids in our understanding of how language operates on social media by depicting an individual's personal evaluation of the circumstances or topics at hand. Semantic models depict cognitive associations linked to the intentional and referential elements of language. We employed van Dijk's (2014) pragmatic or context models to examine their influence on the content, style, and genre of social media discourse. Our focus was on socially and communicatively important aspects of the circumstances. Pragmatic frameworks helped us to understand how the suffering of the Gazans during the war was perceived and communicated through social media.

Van Dijk (2014) asserted that mental models significantly impact perception, interaction, and control over discourse production in several areas of daily life, including discourse production and interpretation. The ability to form mental models depends heavily on the information retained in episodic memory. A mental model is "subjective representations of events or circumstances" (van Dijk, 2014: 49), and it is defined as a framework that helps

categorise and identify current experiences. A person’s subjective account of an event incorporates emotional, cognitive, phenomenological, perceptual, auditory, gestural, and visual experiences (van Dijk, 2018).

1.3. Studies on the Voice of Victims on Social Media

Extensive research has yielded useful insights into social media may facilitate victims’ pain expression. Prier (2020) argues that victims’ narratives of the war on social media serve as a powerful resource for those involved in the fight and how the conflict is shaped. According to Meier (2012), digital media have been praised for empowering and giving voice to individuals who have been silenced by disasters, oppression, and war. Singer and Brooking (2018) concur with Meier (2012) that victims can rapidly and effectively distribute information to a wide audience using social media in isolation resulting from war.

Social media is an exceptionally efficient tool for emergency communications. This facilitates the immediate and rapid dissemination of vital information in real-time. Emergency services have the capacity to disseminate alerts swiftly, offer updates, and provide safety guidance. However, social media also enables the sharing of requests for help and allows prompt responses from individuals who have information about incidents. According to Domalewska (2019), Facebook and Twitter had a significant impact during the May 2019 flood in Poland. Multiple entities, including emergency services, authorities, mass media outlets, individual users, and organisations, utilised both Facebook and Twitter during emergencies. Social media has also substantially influenced the aftermath of the 2011 Japanese earthquake and tsunami. Victims quickly utilised social media within one hour of the earthquake (Vinson, 2011).

The Arab Spring uprisings were precipitated by the pervasive public outrage over structural inequalities, including political oppression, human rights violations, and substantial disparities in wealth and income. The uprisings in late 2010 were the culmination of a protracted period of discontent (Bakis and Karakoç, 2015). Social media significantly influenced the Arab Spring by enabling protesters to communicate and engage with each other. Protesters employed social media to coordinate protests, spread information about their activities, and increase awareness of ongoing events on a local and global scale (Salem and Mourtada, 2011; Al-Ramahi and Ab Rashid, 2019; Kaur et al., 2023). Bhuiyan (2011) argues that the Arab Spring in Egypt was facilitated by social media, particularly Facebook, which enabled the interconnection of activists. Bimber et al. (2005) noted that social media facilitated collective action during the Arab Spring by facilitating collaborative discourse and mobilisation initiatives. Social networking highly influenced the swift and largely peaceful end of dictatorships in Tunisia and Egypt. Social media has played a crucial role in enabling communication between Gazans and people globally throughout the conflict that began on October 7, 2023. Gazans have been able to express their suffering through this type of communication.

Within the arena of social media, victims can break free from their isolation, advocates can amplify their voices, and decision-makers can witness grassroots mobilisation in action (Meraz and Papacharissi, 2013; Castells, 2015; Majul, 2017). Social media has

proven to be highly effective in empowering victims to voice their sentiments, needs, and urgent appeals. However, an important gap in the literature lies in the exploration of how victimhood is discursively constructed and communicated on these platforms, a gap this study aims to address.

2. Methodology

In this discourse analysis-focused study, we collected data from an online Facebook group initially established for shopping, which, starting on October 7, 2023, shifted its focus to the challenging circumstances faced by the people of Gaza. Data was collected from March to June 2024. The time frame selected for data collection was due to the increasing suffering of Gazans. During that time, Israel stepped up its ground and air operations, placing thousands of lives in danger and making it harder for important humanitarian aid to get through. The Israeli army took over and shut down the Rafah border crossing between Egypt and the Gaza Strip. This crossing was the main way that humanitarian aid got in. Throughout this time frame, we collected 95 postings from the Status Updates area of the group. The first author of this paper, who is a native Arabic speaker, translated the original Arabic postings into English. All postings were accessible to anyone with a Facebook account, making them public data (Hyland-Wood, 2023). Using a purposive sampling technique, we selected postings that revolved around Gazan victimhood to form data for this study. As Patton (2002) stated, the logic and efficacy of purposive sampling are contingent on the selection of cases that are information-rich and require further investigation.

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Due to the complexity of the data, we employed manual analysis to ensure we thoroughly captured its intricacies and nuances. Using Patton's (2002) six thematic analysis phases, we familiarised ourselves with the data, conducted a thorough review and took detailed notes to aid the coding process. Next, we created initial codes (e.g., food shortage). Then, we systematically grouped related codes to form broader categories and themes. Once the initial themes were identified, we evaluated them to ensure they reflected consistent patterns in the data. Finally, we refined the themes (e.g., deprivation of basic rights) and used them to generate the report.

In making sense of the themes, we drew on van Dijk's socio-cognitive approach, which is the theoretical underpinning of this research. We scrutinised the syntactic characteristics, lexicalisation, and semantics of the coded material. In other words, we examined the cognitive concepts related to mental models in the coded data, which helped identify the discursive strategies used to develop the themes.

In presenting the analysed data, it is not feasible to include all 95 Facebook posts in full due to word limit constraints. Therefore, we have selected the posts that provide the most clarity in illustrating the identified themes and supporting our arguments. Most of the posts are brief, typically between one to two lines, likely reflecting the challenging conditions of war, which may have hindered the ability to write longer posts.

3. Findings and Discussion

Drawing on van Dijk’s socio-cognitive framework, this study investigates the themes in Gazans’ Facebook postings and reveals how these themes are discursively constructed. The findings can be categorised under the following themes: i) the negative other, referring to the negative perception that Gazans have towards entities such as Israelis and Arabs; ii) deprivation of basic rights, encompassing the challenges faced by Gazans, including starvation, lack of water, and insecurity; iii) a sense of loss, demonstrating the sorrow felt by Gazans for their family members and relatives who lose their lives daily; and iv) positive self-description and satisfaction with fate, emphasising the deep religious belief held by Gazans. These findings highlight the nature of the Gazans as victims. Various discursive strategies emerge in these themes, such as polarisation, concretisation, compassion move, self-identity descriptions, negative lexicalisation, victimisation, hyperbole, and warning.

3.1. The Negative Other

As we go into the theme of the negative other, we discover the glaringly made reality of how the other manifests negativity, either by aggressive actions towards Gazans or through an apathetic attitude towards them. Through a comprehensive analysis of the discourse derived from Facebook postings, the Gazans held a negative view of Israel, the Arab countries, and the world. This perception is influenced by the hatred they encounter with the Israelis and their disappointment with the global community. In the upcoming subsections, we will present our analysis of the discursive strategies that contribute to the construction of the two categories of the negative other, the violent other, and the apathetic other.

3.1.1. The aggressive other

One of the reasons the hostile other is shown in a negative light in the postings is its tendency to engage in acts of violence. In the postings, Israeli troops are consistently portrayed as the primary drivers of devastation, imposing power over the lives of the Gazan people. The following example evokes strong emotions and attracts the attention of receivers.

(1) ‘They bombed the people while they were praying.’ (Posting 16)

Van Dijk (2000) stated that polarisation occurs when two parties engage in deliberate efforts to undermine one another. The deliberate use of footings in the postings of the Gazans impacts how one’s own identity and that of others are depicted. The footing ‘they’ in the clause ‘they were praying’ appears to reflect a positive self-image of Gazans, whereas ‘They’ in the clause ‘They bombed the people’ seems to reflect an adverse perception of others. Posting 16 illustrates the concept of polarisation by emphasising how Israeli armed forces maximise their negative actions through acts of violence such as bombing. Simultaneously, the people of Gaza are portrayed as victims of aggressive actions of their adversaries. We propose that portraying ‘the negative other’ (Israeli armed forces) contributes to the intensification of polarisation, resulting in the construction of Gazan victimisation. The discursive strategy of concretisation also contributes to the construction

of victimisation in Posting 16. Concretisation heightens the negative impression of Israeli soldiers as an outgroup and the positive impression of the Gazans as an ingroup (van Dijk, 2001). Providing full descriptions of the hostile actions ‘They bombed the people’ (Posting 16) carried out by Israeli forces is an integral part of the concretisation strategy.

The violent demeanour of the other is depicted in several postings, with each instance showcasing a distinct form of hostility. We argue that the escalation of the other’s violent disposition contributes to the victimisation of the Gazans.

(2) ‘Anyway... they are taking revenge on us by targeting our children.’ (Posting 7)

Posting 7 constructs the victimhood of the Gazans through the utilisation of polarisation, where the footings ‘they,’ ‘we,’ and ‘our’ create a positive portrayal of self and a negative image of the other. The footing ‘they,’ which represents Israeli armed forces, is portrayed in bad light because it is linked to the activity of seeking revenge. The footings ‘us’ and ‘our,’ which refer to the people of Gaza, are positively conveyed by highlighting the victimisation of Gazan children. This finding, which highlights the commonality of children’s victimisation, is in line with a concept of ‘epistemic communities’ developed by van Dijk (2014), which describes groups of social actors who have been through similar experiences. The utilisation of the concretisation strategy further enhanced the development of victimisation within Posting 7. The manifestation of the violent actions (i.e., targeting our children) committed by the other (Israeli armed forces) serves as evidence of their cruelty, thereby portraying the people of Gaza as victims of these acts. Using physical proof to demonstrate Israeli forces’ cruelty is congruent with van Dijk’s (2014) concept of ‘fact,’ which refers to a verifiable statement or thing that supports a position.

Certain postings disclose the violence that others employ to victimise the people of Gaza. The following example shows the violence committed by Israeli armed forces.

(3) ‘What was your life in prison?’ ‘Terrifying nightmares.’ (Posting 3)

This example contributes to the construction of negative others using the negative lexicalisation strategy ‘prison,’ ‘terrifying,’ and ‘nightmares.’ As indicated in Posting 3, Israeli-operated prison is the source of a terrifying perception. This rhetorical strategy places significant emphasis on the utilisation of a highly derogatory language to characterise the actions of the ‘Other’ (van Dijk, 2014, 2018). Van Dijk (2000) stated that this strategy entails the use of specialised terminology to articulate ideas and perspectives. The hyperbolic strategy is utilised by presenting prison as a nightmarish environment. Hyperbole is a rhetorical technique that involves the use of exaggerated language to describe an event or action (van Dijk, 2001). This strategy enabled the creation of a graphic portrayal of the Israeli armed forces as cruel as well as the construction of an image depicting the people of Gaza as victims.

The utilisation of two discursive strategies, namely, negative lexicalisation and hyperbole, played a significant role in shaping the portrayal of the man in Posting 3 as a victim of the harsh behaviours exhibited by the negative other. The man articulated his personal

knowledge and experience in prison ‘Terrifying nightmares’ (Posting 3). This personal knowledge is consistent with van Dijk’s (2014) ‘episodic memories,’ in which beliefs are personal and based on subjective experiences. We contend that these personal convictions are shared by the Gazan populace because of the substantial number of incarcerated people. This finding agrees with van Dijk’s (2014, 2018) concept of ‘social memory,’ which suggests that beliefs and experiences are no longer considered personal. The shared beliefs and experiences of Gazan community members culminated in a collective fear of prison and the formation of victimhood.

3.1.2. The apathetic other

This theme shows the overall perspective of the Gazans towards the globe and the Arab community. Upon analysing the postings on Facebook, we have identified several essential issues that contribute to the portrayal of this ‘apathetic other.’ This section provides an in-depth review of these issues.

The depiction of the ‘apathetic other’ is unfavourable because it fails to garner support for the Gazan people. Postings illustrate the infeasibility of differentiating this ‘other’ from the one that is prone to violence.

(4) ‘Arabs! Arabs! Your children can eat, drink, sleep, and relax, while our children in Gaza endure famine, illness, oppression, and death.’ (Posting 22)

Posting 22 constructs Gazan victimhood by implementing several discursive strategies. The utilisation of a negative lexicalisation strategy contributes to the establishment of a polarised relationship between the lives of children in Gaza, which are characterised by ‘famine,’ ‘illness,’ ‘oppression,’ ‘death,’ and the lives of Arab children, who can ‘eat,’ ‘drink,’ ‘sleep,’ and ‘relax.’ Through the juxtaposition of ‘Your children’ with ‘our children,’ we argue that this polarisation reduces the children of Gaza to innocent victims. Additionally, the strategy of compassion move contributes to the construction of Gazan victimhood by emphasising the suffering the Gazans endured in the hands of Israel, Arabs, and the global community. An essential component of the compassion move strategy is empathising with the victims of others’ actions to intensify the severity of the ‘Other’ (van Dijk, 1995). We argue that this strategy serves to further polarise the relationship between the situation in Gaza and the global context. This finding aligns with van Dijk’s (2014) ‘context models,’ where the polarised language ‘your children’ and ‘our children’ reflects the real tragic situation in Gaza (e.g., famine). Essentially, the dominant polarised language of ‘our’ and ‘your’ in Posting 22 represents the victimhood of Gazans.

Several Facebook postings reflected this theme. Posting 11 portrays Arabs as the negative ‘other,’ possibly due to their lack of concern for the plight faced by Gazans.

(5) ‘May the Arabs not receive blessings.’ (Posting 11)

The discursive strategies employed to generate this posting primarily involve negative lexicalisation and warning. The utilisation of negative language, such as the phrase, ‘May not receive blessings,’ appears to mirror the disillusionment of Gazans towards Arabs. The

warning in this posting is to remind Arabs that their lack of support for civilian Gazans may prevent them from receiving blessings. The warning strategy focuses on emphasising potential negative behaviours to simultaneously demonise the ‘Other’ and encourage actions within the ingroup (van Dijk, 1995, 2001). We contend that the victimisation of the Gazans is formed by their severe portrayal of Arabs as deprived of blessings. This may indicate their feelings of despair, which in turn manifests as their perception of being victimised.

(6) ‘O Messenger of God, please do not intercede for the Arabs, as they have let us down.’ (Posting 9)

Posting 9 also portrays Arabs in an unfavourable light due to their lack of substantial support. Negative lexicalisation is the main strategy that contributes to the formation of this expression (i.e., letting us down). We argue that the use of negative lexicalisation helps develop an unfavourable perception of Arabs, thereby contributing to the victimisation of Gazans.

(7) ‘Arabs are more preoccupied with entertainment programs than the events unfolding in Gaza.’ (Posting 83)

Posting 83 portrays Arabs in a poor light because of their lack of concern for the dire situation in Gaza. In this posting, the strategy of polarisation served to portray Arabs as indifferent, resulting in insufficient recognition of their victimisation of the Gazans.

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In addition, data analysis revealed that the apathetic other encompasses the entire world. An example of these expressions is:

(8) ‘The world does not see us.’ (Posting 5)

In Posting 5, ‘the world’ and ‘us’ serve as the two components of a polarised structure, contributing to the negative characteristics of the apathetic other. The use of the footing ‘us’ in this sentence highlights Gazans’ victimisation because the world cannot witness their dreadful predicament. Håkansson (2012) argues that using the footing ‘us’ assigns culpability to the ‘other,’ creating a negative portrayal of the opposing group. The negative lexicalisation strategy ‘does not see’ helps with the construction of the negative other, emphasising Gazan victimisation.

3.2 Deprivation of Basic Rights

The findings show that deprivation of basic rights is another prevalent theme identified in the collected postings.

(9) ‘We want to eat; we are hungry in Arabic.’ (Posting 41)

In Posting 41, hunger appeared to be the main theme. The key discursive strategy that constructs Gazans’ victimhood in this posting is polarisation. In our opinion, the speaker’s use of the footing ‘we’ to underscore the collective suffering is indicative of the critical need

for many people. The footing ‘we’ is strategically used to highlight the negative attitudes of others, often associated with the blockade of the Gazans. Our investigation of footings revealed that postings frequently employ van Dijk’s (2014) ‘semantic models,’ which embody an individual’s subjective understanding of their circumstances. By integrating the subjective experiences of Gazans into postings, we can identify Gazans as victims. This finding aligns with the objective of this study, which is to examine the victimisation of Gazans. Posting 41 also employs negative lexicalisation by emphasising hunger and the need to feed, making Gazans appear like victims because they lack necessities.

Another example that centres on the lack of access to essential items considered basic in human life is the following:

(10) ‘The boys killed without having eaten.’ (Posting 33)

Posting 33 demonstrates the use of negative lexicalisation and victimisation as strategies to form the ideological structure of victimisation. The use of negative phrases such as ‘killed’ and ‘without having eaten,’ which are associated with fundamental aspects of human existence, such as the right to life and meeting basic requirements, can contribute to portraying Gazans as victims. Our findings agree with van Dijk’s (2015) ‘communicative situation,’ in which text producers adjust their style and word choices to align with the receiver’s anticipated interests, relevance, and knowledge. Posting 33 also implements a victimisation strategy. The fundamental objective of this strategy is to portray civilian Gazans as victims, while simultaneously emphasising the negative other. There have been attempts to portray ingroup members, civilian Gazans, as genuine victims by incorporating victim narratives and remarks (van Dijk, 2000). The lack of adequate accommodation is also mentioned in the following example.

(11) ‘O God, please alleviate the intense heat experienced by people residing in tents.’
(Posting 75)

In Posting 75, the use of a victimisation strategy contributed to depicting civilian Gazans as people lacking permanent housing, relying solely on inadequate tents for shelter. Presenting the residents of Gaza as people enduring difficult circumstances because of the destruction of their homes helps portray them as victims while also highlighting the violent actions carried out by the other side.

Data analysis shows that the absence of shelters and safety is a recurring theme. It is common for civilians to have trouble securing themselves, particularly when armies are active in urban areas.

(12) ‘We are uncertain about our destination.’ (Posting 39)

This example demonstrates that it is effortless to locate refuge in Gaza. The use of the footings ‘we’ and ‘our’ in this example contributes to the elucidation of the negative others, who are responsible for the loss of shelter and the safety of life. By polarising the ingroup’s difficulty in finding shelter, the portrayal of the Gazan people as victims is emphasised. This finding, together with other comparable findings in this study pertaining

to polarisation, substantiates the significance of polarisation in the realm of social media language (see Cinelli et al., 2021; Persily and Tucker, 2020; Shin and Kadiyala, 2022). Data analysis revealed that lack of public safety was the prevailing theme. Posting 45 illustrates a lack of safety by depicting a young person in a wheelchair with a severed leg.

(13) 'I need my leg back.' (Posting 45)

Concretisation, compassion move, and polarisation are the three strategies that contribute to the construction of victimhood in Posting 45. In this manner, concretisation contributes to the positive ingroup image of the Gazans (van Dijk, 2001). A concretisation strategy was employed to enhance the positive portrayal of the Gazans by providing detailed descriptions of actions taken against civilians, such as the amputation of a child's limb due to bombing. An illustration of the compassionate move strategy in action is the amputation of the child's limb because of conflict. This example also demonstrates empathy through a child's request to restore their limbs. In addition, the employment of polarisation, particularly using the footings 'I' and 'my' in this example, fosters concentration on the child who suffered as the victim and the unfavourable 'other' responsible for the amputation of the leg.

3.3. Sense of Loss

The findings suggest that the most common theme among postings on Gazans is a sense of loss. The analysis also reveals how discursive strategies such as victimisation, hyperbole, compassion move, negative lexicalisation, and polarisation emphasise the negative aspects of the war that have contributed to Gazans' loss while simultaneously promoting their sense of loss.

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The analysis reveals that most postings on Gazans centre on the tragic murder of certain family members, and occasionally the entire family. One example illustrates this phenomenon.

(14) 'My beloved sister was slain.' (Posting 62)

The primary characteristics of this posting framework are concretisation and polarisation strategies. The construction of the positive ingroup involves using the footing 'my' in conjunction with 'beloved sister,' which also concretises the violent act of the hostile other, 'was slain.' This finding resonates with Håkansson (2012), who argues that the use of 'I,' 'my,' 'we,' and 'our' is more effective in expressing the positive self and positive ingroup while positioning the other as negative. Example (15) also considers the violence of the other and the Gazans' sense of loss.

(15) 'He was born in war and died in war.' (Posting 58)

Posting 58 conveyed a profound feeling of grief by employing the strategy of concretisation, wherein birth and death occurred during a war period. This highlights the severity of the situation in Gaza and demonstrates the plight of the Gazan people. The reference to the fleeting nature of life, where there is no time between birth and death, further enhances

the use of hyperbole in constructing Gazans as victims. Hyperbole is the use of highly exaggerated language to describe an event or action (van Dijk, 1995). The use of hyperbole and polarisation played a significant role in the creation of Posting 55.

(16) ‘As if my soul was snatched from me.’ (Posting 55)

Using hyperbole effectively in Posting 55 conveys a profound sense of grief experienced by parents while narrating their children’s murder. We argue that hyperbole, by referring to the boy as ‘my soul’ and characterising the murder as ‘snatched,’ exerts influence over this posting. The strategy of polarisation, achieved by emphasising the usage of the footings ‘my’ and ‘me,’ played a role in building a favourable self-image, while the opposite was true for the other due to the act of soul theft. The profound experience of losing all family members because of war is conveyed in Posting 91.

(17) ‘My spouse and offspring... O God, I beseech you to show compassion towards those whose absence we cannot fully comprehend, and may their resting places be illuminated with radiance and brilliance.’ (Posting 91)

In Posting 91, the use of compassion move and victimisation strategies played a role in shaping the perception of loss. Portraying the complete tragedy experienced by an entire family may help foster comprehension and empathy towards victims of conflict, highlighting their status as victims.

Some postings use phraseology to effectively communicate a sense of loss. Many expressed these emotions in response to war, claiming the lives of their loved ones.

(18) ‘The last hug.’ (Posting 60)

(19) ‘The last look.’ (Posting 59)

(20) ‘Soul of the soul.’ (Posting 57)

Implementing a compassion move strategy helps to foster empathy for the victims of others’ actions, thereby intensifying the severity of the ‘other’s’ behavior (van Dijk, 1995). Postings 57, 59., and 60, which depict the last moments before the burial of civilian casualties from the conflict, greatly enhanced the portrayal of the Gazans as victims. Gilbert’s (2009) concept of compassion, which entails a deep understanding of another person’s pain and a strong desire to alleviate it, aligns perfectly with the intent of these postings, which are primarily structured around this strategy. Although these subjective postings convey personal opinions and feelings, we contend that their dissemination on social media transforms them into widely shared sentiments. This finding aligns with van Dijk’s (2014) assertion that personal attitudes, sentiments, and opinions linked to episodic memory, expressed and supported within the Gazan community, are collectively shared globally among different groups and contribute to social memory. This could be why people worldwide now see the Gazans as victims.

3.4. Positive Self-Description and Satisfaction with Fate

Although themes of positive self-description and satisfaction with fate do not occur frequently, they do exist. One possible reason for their non-recurring nature is the severity of the conditions in which the people of Gaza live, which has led to the emergence of themes strongly linked to the victimisation of the Gazans. Despite being victims of this conflict, these two themes demonstrate the pride that the people of Gaza have in their identity and courage to confront death. Postings on Gazans on Facebook revealed several critical issues that contributed to these themes. We explore these issues further in the following paragraphs.

The theme of positive self-description may symbolise the psychological resilience of victims in Gaza. This theme is evident in this example.

(21) 'We are the people of Gaza, hailing from Shuja'iyya. I am Abu Rami Na'izi, who represents our roots. We are true people, and we are heroes.' (Posting 67)

The strategies of self-identity descriptions and polarisation dominate the ideological structure of Posting 67. The description of Gazans that is communicated in this posting, including 'representing our roots,' 'We are true people,' and 'we are heroes' contributed to the construction of Gazans' positive self-representation. Van Dijk's (1995, 2001) strategy of self-identity descriptions, which emphasises the positive attributes of a group when it is under attack by another group, is consistent with our analysis. Van Dijk (2001) attributes the positive aspects of personal, cultural, and institutional characteristics to 'us.' Polarisation, which is an integral part of the ideological framework of Posting 67, also serves to emphasise the positive self-representation of Gazans. This posting employs the footings 'we' and 'our' constantly, which are connected to a sense of unity and a way of presenting oneself in a positive light (Håkansson, 2012). Our contention is that the focus on positive self-description may serve as a means of portraying Gazans as victims because they differ from the 'negative other.' Another example of a positive self-description is

(22) 'We will not abandon Gaza, even if it means our death.' (Posting 66)

As shown in Posting 66, the combination of polarisation and victimisation strategies creates an ideologically produced statement. The words 'not abandon Gaza' and the reference to 'our death' give a sense that Gazans are victims. This victimisation paints a positive image of the Gazan. Using the footings 'our' and 'we' created a polarised structure that, in addition to victimisation, helped Gazans portray themselves as victims by projecting a positive image of themselves while simultaneously projecting a negative image of the force that might cause them to die or flee their country.

Fate satisfaction was a recurrent theme in some postings. Two ways Gazans express their contentment with their lives are by giving thanks to God for everything and feeling proud of dying for Allah (Shaheed). Posting 70 illustrates this plainly:

(23) 'May You be satisfied, O Lord, and all thanks belong to You.' (Posting 70)

We contend that Posting 70 demonstrates the vulnerability and positive nature of the Gazans, making them victims of conflict. By offering gratitude and imploring the Lord, they may develop the conviction that conflict can be resolved. Our findings are in line with those of Al-Seheel et al. (2016), who found a link between positive psychology and the significant function of gratitude in Islamic culture during hardship. Posting 69 is another example of Gazans’ satisfaction with their circumstances:

(24) ‘We are all projects of martyrs.’ (Posting 69)

The use of polarisation and victimisation strategies has played a significant role in shaping the ideological framework of Posting 69. In this context, the footing ‘We’ refers to the Gazan people who willingly sacrifice their lives as the cause of Gaza. The victimisation strategy portrays ‘We’ (Gazans) as victims of an indescribable conflict. Furthermore, hyperbole played a role in shaping this posting by depicting death as ‘projects of martyrs,’ which is consistent with van Dijk’s (2001, 2004) interpretation of hyperbole as a form of extreme exaggeration in describing a state or an action.

Conclusion

This study examined 95 Facebook postings on the Gazans, focusing on their postings regarding the war that occurred after October 7, 2023. Van Dijk’s socio-cognitive model served as the theoretical framework for this investigation, as well as a base for discursive strategies that disclose victimised Gazans. These strategies are closely associated with the semantic and contextual models proposed by van Dijk’s socio-cognitive model. The findings of this study reveal several themes that revolve around the victimhood of the Gazans, such as negative others, denial of fundamental rights, sense of loss, positive self-description, and contentment with fate. These themes highlight the hostile other (the enemy), the indifferent other, the deprivation of necessities, the terrible loss of family members, the psychological fortitude of Gaza victims, and the contentment of Gazans regarding their destiny.

Our findings reveal that several discursive strategies were employed in the postings, which contributed to portraying the Gazans as victims. These strategies include polarisation, concretisation, compassion move, self-identity descriptions, negative lexicalisation, victimisation, hyperbole, and warning. This study provides new perspectives on the current body of research on the linguistic characteristics of victimisation in social media discourse. We anticipate that these findings will help to expand the corpus of evidence by illustrating the construction of victimhood on social media. By examining both the theoretical and practical aspects of how social media generates and disseminates concepts associated with victimhood, this study significantly advances the field of media research.

Nevertheless, this study has some limitations. The data collection period for Facebook postings spanned only three months, specifically from March to June 2024. In addition, the study used only a limited portion of accessible literature: 95 postings containing small stories, remarks, and prayers. Because our study was qualitative, we prioritised picking

examples that provided a significant amount of information for thorough analysis rather than focusing on the quantity of data. Another limitation arises from the logical application of van Dijk's cognitive concepts in data analysis. This study examined eight cognitive categories that could potentially restrict the discursive strategies that shape perceptions of victimhood.

The findings of this study should motivate reassessment of the extent to which social media contributes to the concept of victimhood. Future research that explores innovative concepts in the field of social media has the potential to enhance the current corpus of knowledge on the subject, given that this study focuses only on Gazan victimhood. Follow-up investigations should examine this topic in the broader context of media.

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